

Indolizines : A Comparative Study of the Synthesis from Pyridinium Bromides and Iodides

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Synthesis of α -picolinium derivatives using two procedures, (i) by the quaternisation with acylmethylene bromides and (ii) by Kings method involving the reaction between α -picoline, iodine and a methyl ketone which on cyclisation leads to the formation of indolizines, were studied. Comparison of the yield from the two procedures showed that the second method can be used as an alternate procedure especially with ketones which either do not yield stable α -bromo derivatives or undergo bromination at other positions in the molecule.

COUPLING Kings reaction¹ with Tschitschibabin² cyclisation has been reported to be a convenient route in the synthesis of aza substituted indolizines. Borrows and Holland³ reported that the same procedure, in the case of indolizines, results in very low yield of the final products. This procedure should be particularly useful for ketones which do not yield the required α -halo derivatives by normal halogenation. Here we report the results of a comparative study of the two procedures leading to the formation of indolizines.

Indolizines (1-5) were prepared using two procedures. In the first method (A), phenacyl bromides obtained in 70-80% yield by direct bromination of the corresponding ketone in ether were used for quaternisation of α -picoline. The quaternary salts (yield 65-75%) were converted to the 2-arylindolizines by treatment with sodium bicarbonate. The overall yield of indolizines based on the amount of arylmethyl ketone taken was 50-55%. In the second method (B), α -picoline taken in excess (~3 mol per mol of ketone) was treated with the corresponding ketones and iodine (1 mol). The picolinium iodides could be separated only in 40-45% yield. Further cyclisation of the iodides gave 48-55% yield of indolizines. Yield of indolizines comparable with those obtained in method-A (35-40%) could be obtained if the reaction mixture is directly treated with sodium bicarbonate without initial separation of the iodides. The identity of the final products obtained by both the methods were also confirmed.

Comparison of the yield from the two procedures shows that the second procedure can be used as an alternate method especially with ketones which either do not yield stable α -bromo derivatives or undergo bromination at other positions in the molecule.

With acetone, both the procedures yielded the quaternary salts which could not be separated in pure form. The products of quaternisation were

directly converted to indolizine (6, 55% by method-A, 19% by method-B) which can easily be separated by steam distillation.

Method-B was found to be successful in the preparation of 2-furyl substituted indolizine (7). *N*-Furoyl methylene- α -picolinium iodide which was not isolated from the Kings reaction mixture yielded 25% of 2-(2-furyl)indolizine by cyclisation with sodium bicarbonate. Indolizines (8-12) were also obtained by the same method in 8-17% yield. The intermediate picolinium iodides were not isolated in pure form.

Experimental

The ketones (G.R.) were used. Melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the products were ascertained by tlc using silica gel (Merck G.E. 254). Satisfactory elemental analysis were obtained for all the compounds.

Mass spectra were recorded on a Hewlett-Packerd 5995 spectrometer operating at 70 eV, nmr spectra on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard, electronic spectra (MeOH) on a Hitachi-220A spectrophotometer (showed mainly two absorption bands nearly

at 230 and 300 nm), and ir spectra (KBr) recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer (which did not give much information in analysing the structure of the compounds).

Method-A: ω -Bromoacetophenones were prepared by direct bromination⁴. To a well-cooled solution of α -picoline (0.1 mol) in dry ethanol (20 ml), brominated ketones (0.1 mol) were added and the spontaneous exothermal reaction was controlled by external cooling. The reaction mixture was then left overnight. The hard mass formed was powdered, washed with ice-cold ethanol (50 ml), crystallised from boiling ethanol to afford shining pale yellow crystals of α -picolinium bromides (1b-5b) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF PHENACYL- α -PICOLINIUM IODIDES (1a-5a) AND BROMIDES (1b-5b)

R	Yield %/(M.p., °C)	
	X=I (1a-5a)	X=Br (1b-5b)
Phenyl	40 (204)	75 (214)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	45 (190)	73 (146)
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	42 (210)	71 (186)
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	35 (212)	65 (222)
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	45 (206)	70 (176)

The phenacyl- α -picolinium bromides (1b-5b; 0.1 mol) were dissolved in warm water, sodium bicarbonate solution (20%) was added and the mixture boiled for about 10 min. On cooling, the indolizines (1-5) separated as iridescent platelets. After 30 min, the solid was removed and the filtrate again boiled to yield a further quantity of the product. The combined crops were washed well with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

Method-B: To a mixture of ketone (0.1 mol) and excess α -picoline (\sim 0.3 mol), iodine (0.1 mol) was added portionwise with efficient stirring. After the moderate exothermic reaction subsided, the mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for about 45 min. After leaving the reaction mixture

overnight, the resulting thick syrup was poured into water (300 ml) and the heterogeneous mixture was shaken with ether to remove most of the black oil. The aqueous solution was filtered through kieselguhr to remove the remainder of the oil and then clarified with charcoal. The filtrate on concentration yielded shining crystals of α -picolinium iodides (1a-5a), whereas picoline hydriodide remained in the aqueous solution.

The α -picolinium iodides (1a-5a; 0.01 mol) were dissolved in hot water and a solution of sodium bicarbonate (20%) was added till the effervescence ceased. The aqueous solution was then heated on a water-bath for about 10 min and then cooled. The precipitated indolizines (1-5) were crystallised from ethanol as iridescent platelets.

The α -picolinium iodides obtained from acetone, 2-acetylfuran, ethyl methyl ketone, methyl propyl ketone, isopropyl methyl ketone, cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone could not be separated in crystalline form. So the crude mixture was treated with sodium bicarbonate and heated on a water-bath for 10 min. 2-(2-Furylindolizine) separated as crystals were filtered off and crystallised from ethanol. The other alkyl indolizines were separated by steam distillation.

Compounds for which physical data were not reported earlier were identified by nmr and mass spectral data. *p*-Methyl-2-phenylindolizine (3): *m/e* 207 (M^+ , 100), 206 (30.2), 205 (5), 204 (10.9), 203 (1.4), 192 (4.1), 191 (10.1), 190 (2.9), 180 (1.8), 178 (3), 177 (1.4), 176 (1.9), 167 (2), 165 (2.7), 164 (1.7), 152 (2.4), 151 (1.6), 129 (1.7), 128 (3.6), 127 (2.5), 115 (2.3), 103 (6.9), 102 (8), 95 (1.5) and 90 (3.6); δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.12-6.65 (3H, m, H₁, H₆ and H₇), 7.04 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, H₈ and H₉), 7.4 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, H₂ and H₅), 7.14-7.95 (2H, m, H₃ and H₄) and 7.45 (1H, m, H₁₀). 2-(2-Furyl)indolizine (7): *m/e* 183 (M^+ , 100), 156 (2.3), 155 (27.9), 154 (70.6), 152 (7.6), 129 (2.3), 128 (4.4), 127 (9), 126 (4), 125 (2.7), 116 (4), 114 (1.4), 104 (1.3), 103 (2), 102 (4), 101 (7) and 100 (1.8); in nmr spectra, the complexity of the multiplets in the aromatic region did

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF INDOLIZINES (1-12)

Compd. no	R	Yield (%)		M p. (°C)			Mol. weight	Mol. formula
		X=Br	X=I	Observed	Reported	Picrate		
1	Phenyl	72	50	215	215 ^a	—	193	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N
2	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	75	55	248	248 ^b	—	227	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ NOCl
3	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	76	55	215	—	—	207	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N
4	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	70	48	246	246 ^c	—	238	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂
5	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	75	52	205	205 ^d	—	223	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ NO
6	Methyl	55	19	59.5	59.5 ^a	118	131	C ₉ H ₉ N
7	Furyl-2	—	25	197	—	—	188	C ₁₂ H ₉ NO
8	Ethyl	45	15	41	41 ^e	104-05	145	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N
9	Propyl	32	15	37	—	160	159	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N
10	Isopropyl	35	17	35	—	161	159	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N
11	Cyclopenta[2,3]indolizine	—	8	43	—	154	157	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N
12	Cyclohexa[2,3]indolizine	—	10	52	52 ^e	159	171	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N

*Lit.: ^aRef. 3, ^bRef. 5, ^cRef. 6, ^dRef. 7, ^eRef. 8.

not allow complete assignment of the signals. **2-Propylindolizine (9)**: m/e 159 (M^+ , 38.5), 145 (7.3), 144 (30.5), 143 (9.6), 142 (11.5), 132 (10.9), 131 (100), 130 (92.9), 128 (10.7), 117 (13.6), 104 (7.5), 103 (13), 102 (10) and 93 (6.3); δ 0.86 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.26–1.96 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.65 (2H, t, CH_2), 6.2–6.72 (3H, m, H_1 , H_6 and H_7) and 7.05–7.8 (3H, m, H_2 , H_5 and H_8). **2-Isopropylindolizine (10)**: m/e 159 (M^+ , 95.2), 158 (48), 145 (37.6), 144 (100), 143 (43.2), 142 (40.8), 141 (26.8), 131 (12), 130 (9.6), 118 (20.8), 117 (34.8), 116 (18), 115 (31.2) and 93 (12.4); δ 1.22 (6H, d, J 7.5 Hz, CH_3), 2.6–3.35 (1H, m, J 7.5 Hz, CH), 6.22–6.75 (3H, m, H_1 , H_6 and H_7) and 7.1–7.85 (3H, m, H_2 , H_5 and H_8). **Cyclopenta[2,3]indolizine (11)**: m/e 157 (M^+ , 80), 156 (100), 154 (20), 141 (6), 130 (7), 129 (4), 128 (8) and 117 (3); nmr spectra not recorded due to its instability.

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